

Indole-based hydrazide-hydrazone and sulfonylhydrazone derivatives as MAO-B inhibitors with multitarget potential for neurodegenerative diseases

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Abstract

Given the complex, multifactorial nature of Parkinson’s and Alzheimer’s diseases (PD and AD), along with the limited effectiveness of single-target treatments, multi-target-directed ligands (MTDLs) present a promising alternative approach. Monoamine oxidases A and B (MAO-A, MAO-B), as well as acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE), are key targets in the development of MTDLs. In our previous study, we developed melatonin–donepezil hybrids with hydrazone (3a–r) and sulfonylhydrazone (5a–l) scaffolds, which showed AChE/BChE inhibition, antioxidant activity, low neurotoxicity, blood–brain barrier permeability, and Aβ₄₂ reduction. This study focused on their MAO-B inhibition. Compounds 3e, 3f, 3i, and 3r showed dual MAO-B/MAO-A inhibition, while 5a and 5c were selective for MAO-B. Docking confirmed strong binding, especially for 3e and 3f. Despite moderate CYP3A4 inhibition (~30–35%) by some compounds, 3e, 3f, 3i, 3r, 5a, and 5c exhibited promising multitarget activity and are strong candidates for further optimization to enhance MAO-B selectivity while minimizing drug–drug interaction risks.

Keywords

hydrazide-hydrazones, monoamine oxidase B inhibitors, sulfonylhydrazones, CYP3A4

Introduction

Monoamine oxidases (MAOs) are flavin-containing enzymes responsible for the oxidative deamination of neurotransmitters and dietary amines, playing a pivotal role in maintaining neurochemical balance. MAOs exist as two isoforms, MAO-A and MAO-B, each characterized by distinct

substrate preferences and tissue distributions (Al-Nuaimi et al. 2012; Yeung et al. 2019; Kot 2025). MAO-A primarily metabolizes serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine, with inhibitors like moclobemide used to treat depression (Stahl and Felker 2008; Finberg and Rabey 2016; Naoi et al. 2025). However, MAO-A inhibitors carry the risk of the “cheese effect”—a hypertensive crisis triggered by tyramine

accumulation from certain foods (Finberg and Rabey 2016; Naoi et al. 2025). MAO-B, on the other hand, selectively breaks down dopamine and phenylethylamine, particularly in the brain. Selective, irreversible MAO-B inhibitors such as selegiline and rasagiline target this pathway, preserving dopamine levels without significantly affecting serotonin or norepinephrine at therapeutic doses (Oyovwi et al. 2025). This selectivity minimizes dietary restrictions, making MAO-B inhibitors safer and more effective in managing Parkinson's disease (PD), a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by dopaminergic neuron loss in the substantia nigra (Dezsi and Vecsei 2017; Jost 2022; Oyovwi et al. 2025). Notably, studies reveal an age-associated up-regulation of MAO-B in PD patients (Bar-Am et al. 2015), accelerating dopamine degradation and contributing to disease progression (Rahman et al. 2021). By inhibiting MAO-B, these drugs help sustain endogenous dopamine, extend levodopa's efficacy, and may offer neuroprotective benefits (Parambi 2020). Additionally, they exhibit a more favorable safety profile than many other PD treatments (Regensburger et al. 2023). The recent FDA approval of safinamide in 2017—a reversible, selective MAO-B inhibitor—reflects ongoing efforts to enhance therapeutic outcomes with improved safety profiles (Parambi 2020; Aboulatta et al. 2023). Despite these advancements, current MAO-B inhibitors still present challenges, including irreversible binding, side effects, and drug–drug interactions (Edinoff et al. 2022). These limitations fuel ongoing efforts to develop novel, reversible MAO-B inhibitors with enhanced selectivity, improved safety, and optimized therapeutic potential—critical for advancing PD treatment strategies.

Emerging evidence supports the therapeutic potential of MAO-B inhibitors beyond PD, particularly in Alzheimer's disease (AD). Elevated MAO-B expression has been detected in reactive astrocytes within AD brains, contributing to oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and amyloid pathology—key drivers of AD progression (Weinreb et al. 2016; Jaisa-Aad et al. 2024; Nam et al. 2024). By inhibiting MAO-B, these pathological processes may be attenuated, suggesting a dual role for MAO-B inhibitors in both symptom management and slowing disease progression (Finberg and Rabey 2016). This expanding therapeutic horizon underscores the importance of developing novel MAO-B inhibitors with improved selectivity, safety, and efficacy—crucial for advancing treatments for PD, AD, and other neurodegenerative conditions.

Because Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD) are complex, multifactorial neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) with diverse pathological mechanisms and given the limited efficacy of single-target therapies, which offer only temporary symptom relief without slowing disease progression (Goncalves et al. 2021), a multi-target-directed ligand (MTDL) approach has emerged as a promising alternative (Ramsay et al. 2016; Herrera-Arozamena et al. 2022). This strategy aims to simultaneously target multiple pathological pathways, including cholinesterase (ChE) and monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibition, along with amyloid-beta (A β) aggregation, to restore neurotransmitter balance and counteract neurodegeneration. Additionally, MTDL compounds

show potential for addressing AD/PD-related comorbidities like anxiety and sleep disturbances. This multidirectional approach holds significant promise for more effective neurodegenerative disease (NDD) therapeutics (Mathew et al. 2019).

In our previous study, we designed, synthesized, and evaluated two novel series of hybrid molecules combining melatonin and donepezil structures, incorporating either hydrazone (3a–r) or sulfonyl hydrazone (5a–l) fragments as multifunctional agents targeting Alzheimer's disease (AD)-related neurodegenerative pathways (Angelova et al. 2023). Their pharmacological profiles were assessed based on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibition, antioxidant activity (DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays), and lipid peroxidation inhibition in the linoleic acid system. The compounds were also evaluated for neurotoxicity in normal murine fibroblast cells (CCL-1) (Table 1), demonstrating promising biocompatibility. The PAMPA-BBB model confirmed that most compounds exhibited the ability to cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Molecular docking studies identified some compounds as potential multitargeted agents, capable of binding to MT1 and MT2 melatonin receptors, along with AChE and BChE enzymes. Further study explores the lead compounds' effects on key pathological features of Alzheimer's disease (AD) in both cellular and *in vivo* models [24]. An enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was employed to assess the anti-fibrillogenic properties of 15 selected derivatives, quantifying changes in neurotoxic β -amyloid (A β 42) formation in human neuronal cells following treatment (Mihaylova et al. 2024). These encouraging results provide early insights into emerging disease-modifying strategies, highlighting the potential of these multifunctional hybrids to combine synergistic neuroprotective activities within a single molecule.

The goal of this study was to evaluate 30 novel hydrazone–hydrazone and sulfonylhydrazone derivatives for their monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitory activities, with a focus on identifying potent and selective MAO-B inhibitors. The aim was to uncover promising lead compounds for the development of safer, more effective therapies for Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD). Additionally, targeting multiple therapeutic pathways while minimizing interactions with the cytochrome P450 (CYP) system offers a significant advantage in addressing the complex nature of neurodegeneration.

Materials and methods

General method

Reagents used in the synthetic and pharmacological experimental work were purchased from E. Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

Chemistry

Synthetic procedure for the preparation of hydrazone derivatives: A solution of substituted carbaldehydes

(2 mmol) 4 in absolute ethanol was added to a solution of the suitable hydrazide 1 (2 mmol) in absolute ethanol with vigorous stirring. The solution was heated under reflux for 1–3 hours (Angelova et al. 2023). The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) using hexane:ethyl acetate (8:2) as the eluent. The formed solid product was collected by filtration and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the targeted hydrazones.

MAO inhibitory in vitro assay

The Amplex® Red Hydroxyl Peroxidase (HRP) Assay Kit provides a sensitive method using Amplex® Red (10-acetyl-3,7-dihydroxy-phenoxazine) reagent for the detection of hydrogen peroxide or peroxidase activity in biological samples or enzyme-coupled reactions. In the presence of peroxidase, the Amplex® Red reagent reacts 1:1 stoichiometrically with hydrogen peroxide, producing a red phosphorescent oxidation product, resorufin.

Due to its high extinction coefficient ($58,000 \pm 5,000 \text{ cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{M}^{-1}$), analysis can be performed fluorometrically or spectrophotometrically (Bautista-Aguilera et al. 2014). The reaction is used to detect small amounts of hydrogen peroxide (on the order of 10 pM, in a volume of 100 μL).

The experiment was performed according to the following protocol: Solutions were prepared following the manufacturer's instructions, and a stock solution of Amplex® Red (10 mM) was prepared by dissolving the reagent in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The reaction buffer consisting of 0.05 M sodium phosphate (pH 7.4) was obtained by diluting a concentrated solution provided in the kit with distilled water. The HRP storage solution (10 U/mL) was prepared by dissolving HRP powder in reaction buffer; 1 U was defined as the amount of enzyme (hMAO-A/B) that forms 1.0 mg of purpurugalin from pyrogallol in 20 seconds at pH 6.0 and 4.3.

CYP3A4 inhibition assay – Fluorometric method for determination of the activity of the CYP3A4 isoform of human recombinant cytochrome P450

The inhibitory activity of test compounds on the CYP3A4 isoform of human recombinant cytochrome P450 was evaluated using the CYP3A4 Inhibitor Screening Kit, with resorufin as the substrate and ketoconazole as the reference inhibitor.

Sample preparation

Lyophilized standards were dissolved in 110 μL of DMSO (5 mM), vortexed, and stored at -20°C for up to three freeze/thaw cycles. The NADPH-generating system was reconstituted in 220 μL of CYP assay buffer and kept on ice during the procedure. β -NADP⁺ stock (100 \times) was dissolved in 110 μL of CYP buffer (10 mM NADP⁺) and stored at -20°C . The CYP substrate was dissolved in 110 μL of anhydrous HPLC-grade acetonitrile (5 mM stock) and stored at -20°C . The CYP inhibitor was

dissolved in 110 μL of acetonitrile (1 mM stock), stored at -20°C , and used within two months. A working solution (2.5 μM) was prepared by diluting 5 μL of stock in 1995 μL of CYP buffer. Lyophilized recombinant human CYP enzyme was dissolved in 230 μL of CYP assay buffer, mixed with 20 μL of NADPH-generating system (100 \times), and stored at -80°C . The enzyme solution was shaken before use and remained stable for one month, losing approximately 10% activity per week.

Standard preparation

A 200 μM standard was prepared by diluting 10 μL of 5 mM stock in 240 μL of CYP assay buffer, then further diluted to 1 μM (1 pmol/ μL) for standard curve preparation.

Cell lysate preparation

Microsomes were isolated from liver cells using a Microsome Isolation Kit. Fifty milligrams of tissue or 5×10^6 cells were homogenized in 500 μL of ice-cold CYP buffer, incubated on ice for 5 minutes, and centrifuged at $15,000 \times g$ for 15 minutes at 4°C . The supernatant was collected and kept on ice. For human liver microsomes, 25 μg of protein per well was used, while liver S9 fractions required 50–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{well}$.

Test compound preparation

Test ligands were dissolved in appropriate solvents and diluted to $5 \times$ working concentration with CYP Assay Buffer. Acetonitrile ($\leq 1\%$ final concentration) was preferred to avoid interference with CYP activity, as DMSO $\geq 0.25\%$ (v/v) significantly inhibits CYP activity.

Procedure

All reagents and samples were brought to room temperature before use. Two parallel sample sets were prepared.

Reaction setup: Each reaction (50 μL) contained 2 μL of NADPH-generating system (100 \times) and 2–48 μL of the test sample, adjusted to 50 μL with CYP Buffer.

Measurement

Fluorescence was measured at excitation/emission wavelengths of 406/468 nm using a microplate reader in kinetic mode for 60 minutes at 37°C . The reaction started immediately after adding the CYP substrate/NADP⁺ mix, so the microplate reader settings were pre-configured. Data collection was performed in kinetic mode, with time points (T_1 and T_2) selected within the linear range of the reaction.

This protocol ensured accurate evaluation of CYP3A4 inhibition and identified potential drug–drug interaction risks associated with the tested compounds.

Statistical analysis

The results obtained on the human recombinant MAO-A/B enzyme (hMAO-A/B) and CYP3A4 were statistically processed using Student's t-test with statistical significance set at $P < 0.05$.

Table 1. IC₅₀ (or EC₅₀) values of the most active compounds 3e, 3f, 3i, 3r (series 3a–r) and 5a, 5c (series 5a–l), along with reference inhibitors (chlorgyline and selegiline), against human monoamine oxidase isoforms (hMAO-A and hMAO-B). In vitro cytotoxicity was evaluated via IC₅₀ values in normal murine fibroblast cells (CCL-1).

Compd.	Structure	hMAOB IC ₅₀ (EC ₅₀), (μM ± SD) ^a	hMAOA IC ₅₀ (EC ₅₀), (μM ± SD) ^a	SI ^b	CCL-1 ^c IC ₅₀ μM
3a		-	-	-	138.5 ± 9.8
3b		-	-	-	153.5 ± 7.3
3c		-	-	-	167.8 ± 10.4
3d		-	-	-	220
3e		0.662 ± 0.10	0.598 ± 0.09	0.903	>300
3f		0.524 ± 0.20	0.978 ± 0.20	1.866	150 ± 11.2
3g		-	-	-	>300
3h		-	-	-	>300
3i		0.633 ± 0.10	0.488 ± 0.10	0.771	>800
3j		-	-	-	>300
3k		-	-	-	>300
3l		-	-	-	>300
3m		-	-	-	65.4 ± 5.1
3n		-	-	-	48.2 ± 6.4
3o		-	-	-	>300

Compd.	Structure	hMAOB IC ₅₀ (EC ₅₀), (μM ± SD) ^a	hMAOA IC ₅₀ (EC ₅₀), (μM ± SD) ^a	SI ^b	CCL-1 ^c IC ₅₀ μM
3p		-	-	-	>300
3q		-	-	-	170.2 ± 14.0
3r		0.611 ± 0.20	0.561 ± 0.20	0.918	>300
5a		0.855 ± 0.10	>100	>117	156.9 ± 8.5
5b		-	-	-	38.1 ± 3.5
5c		0.849 ± 0.20	>100	>118	25.7 ± 2.9
5d		-	-	-	140.3 ± 8.4
5e		-	-	-	180 ± 9.6
5f		-	-	-	167.4 ± 11.8
5g		-	-	-	50.7 ± 3.6
5h		-	-	-	159.6
5i		-	-	-	147.3
5j		-	-	-	41.2 ± 4.2
5k		-	-	-	321.4 ± 16.2
5l		-	-	-	131.4 ± 11.4
	Selegiline	0.320 ± 0.09	-	-	-
	Chlorgyline	-	0.355 ± 0.09	-	-

^aValues are expressed as the mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM) from at least three independent experiments, each performed in quadruplicate.

^bSI: hMAO-B selectivity index = IC₅₀(hMAO-A)/IC₅₀(hMAO-B).

^cThe IC₅₀ values for normal murine fibroblast cells (CCL-1), as reported in our previous study (Angelova et al. 2023), provide insight into the cytotoxicity and biocompatibility of the tested compounds.

Molecular docking study

Molecular docking studies were performed using the docking tool of the Molecular Operating Environment (MOE, version 2022.02, <https://www.chemcomp.com/Products.htm>). The crystal structure of human monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B) complexed with (S)-(+)-2-[4-(fluorobenzyloxy-benzyl-amino)propionamide] (SAG) and co-factor flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) was used (Protein Data Bank, PDB ID 2V5Z, <http://www.rcsb.org/>). The protein–ligand complex was protonated at pH 7.4. During docking, water molecules were removed, while the co-factor FAD was retained.

Structure preparation

The 3D structures of the investigated compounds were built and optimized using AMBER10:EHT in MOE. The PDB complexes were prepared using the “Quick preparation” procedure in MOE. This included adding hydrogens and assigning protonation states of titratable protein groups by the Generalized Born electrostatics model under physiological conditions (temperature 300 K; pH 7.4; ion concentration 0.1 mol/L). Tethers were added to receptor heavy atoms, and distant atoms were fixed. System refinement was performed applying the Amber10:EHT force field with a default RMS gradient of 0.1 kcal/mol/Å².

Prediction of the protonation state of the investigated structures

The “Protomer” panel in MOE was used to explore possible ionization states of the molecules at physiological pH. Ionization states were sorted by decreasing population, and the state with the highest population percentage at physiological pH was used for docking.

Docking simulations

Docking was performed in MOE’s “Docking” module using the following settings: (I) “Triangle Matcher” placement generated poses by systematically aligning ligand atom triplets with triplets of alpha spheres; the London dG scoring function ranked the poses (30 placement poses). (II) Subsequent refinement employed either the “Rigid receptor” or “Induced fit” (flexible side chains) protocols, using London dG and GBVI/WSA scoring functions, yielding 5 final poses after refinement. The London dG scoring function estimates the ligand binding free energy from a given pose by combining enthalpy and entropy contributions. The GBVI/WSA dG is a force field–based scoring function used for rescoring to refine the final docking poses. Protein–ligand interactions within the active site were visualized using MOE’s “Ligand Interactions” tool.

Results and discussion

Chemistry

The synthetic routes for hydrazide–hydrazones (3a–r) and sulfonyl–hydrazones (5a–l) were described in our previous study (Angelova et al. 2023). A series of aldehydes were

reacted with hydrazides or sulfonylhydrazides in absolute ethanol under reflux, with reaction times varying depending on the reagents used. The structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS). The final structures of all tested compounds are presented in Table 1.

Biological evaluation

Evaluation of two series of compounds on human recombinant MAO-B and MAO-A activity

The tested compounds are categorized into four groups based on their structural characteristics. In our previous study (Angelova et al. 2023), MTT assays were conducted on normal murine fibroblast cells (CCL-1) to assess the *in vitro* biocompatibility of the tested compounds (shown in Table 1). The resulting half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values suggested a favorable cytotoxic profile for most compounds in both series, with IC₅₀ values approaching or exceeding 100 μM.

The first group comprised *N*-benzylpiperidine-containing hydrazide-hydrazones (3a–3d) and an *N*-benzylpiperidine analogue containing a sulfonyl-hydrazone fragment (5a) (Table 1). Although the compounds contained a donepezil fragment and demonstrated acetylcholinesterase inhibition (Angelova et al. 2023) and notable anti-Aβ activity (Mihaylova et al. 2024), they exhibited no significant inhibitory activity against MAO-A and MAO-B (Figs 1–4).

Only the sulfonyl-hydrazone derivative 5a, containing a donepezil fragment, exhibited a pronounced and statistically significant inhibitory effect against hMAO-B, reducing enzyme activity by 40%, comparable to the inhibition observed with selegiline (Fig. 4, Table 1). Additionally, compound 5a demonstrated the strongest AChE and BChE inhibitory activity in its series, along with low cytotoxicity in normal murine fibroblast cells (CCL-1) (Table 1).

From the pyrrolidine-containing hydrazone derivatives (3e–i, second group), on hMAO-A activity (Fig. 1), only 3e, 3f, and 3i displayed statistically significant inhibitory activity compared to the control (pure MAO-A), reducing enzyme activity by 55%, 40%, and 70%, respectively. Notably, 3i showed more potent inhibitory activity on hMAO-A than Chlorgyline. Regarding hMAO-B activity (Fig. 3), again, only 3e, 3f, and 3i exhibited strong, statistically significant inhibitory effects. These compounds did not show selectivity for MAO-B, with the exception of 3f (Fig. 3). Additionally, the compounds in this series (3e–i) containing *o*-, *p*-dihydroxy groups in the benzene ring (3f) and *o,p*-trihydroxy groups (3h) exhibited modest inhibitory activity against both acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase (Angelova et al. 2023). Notably, compound 3e demonstrated significant anti-Aβ activity (Mihaylova et al. 2024). These findings highlight the potential of 3f and 3i as multi-target-directed ligands (MTDLs) for therapies targeting multiple neurodegenerative pathways.

Figure 1. Effect of compounds 3a-r and chorglyline in 1 μ M concentration on the activity of hMAO-A. *** $P < 0.001$ compared to control (pure hMAO-A).

Figure 2. Effect of compounds 5a-l and chorglyline in 1 μ M concentration on the activity of hMAO-A. *** $P < 0.001$ compared to control (pure hMAO-A).

Figure 3. Effect of compounds 3a-r and selegiline in 1 μ M concentration on the activity of hMAO-B. *** $P < 0.001$ compared to control (pure hMAO-B).

The third group, consisting of *tert*-butyl-2-hydrazinyl-2-oxoethylcarbamate compounds (3j–3m) with various indole ring substitutions, did not exhibit statistically significant MAO-A/B inhibitory activity (Figs 1, 3) or inhibition against AChE and BChE (Angelova et al. 2023). However, hydrazinyl-2-oxoethylcarbamate derivatives 3k and 3l reduced A β ₄₂ levels by 15- and 30-fold, respectively, showing the most significant downregulation of A β ₄₂ (Mihaylova et al. 2024), along with minimal cytotoxicity

in normal murine fibroblast cells (CCL-1) as described previously (Angelova et al. 2023) (Table 1).

The fourth group, composed of hydrazide-hydrazone derivatives (3n–r) and their sulfonyl-hydrazone analogs (5b–l), featured varied substitutions in both the melatonin fragment and benzene ring. However, none of these compounds exhibited satisfactory inhibitory activity against hMAO-A, except 3r, which reduced MAO-A activity by 45% (Fig. 1). Notably, 3r also demonstrated a potent and

Figure 4. Effect of compounds 5a-l and selegiline in 1 μ M concentration on the activity of hMAO-B. *** $P < 0.001$ compared to control (pure hMAO-B).

statistically significant inhibitory effect on hMAO-B, reducing enzyme activity by 50% (Fig. 3, Table 1). Since 3r inhibited both MAO-A and MAO-B with similar potency, it may be classified as a non-selective inhibitor with low cytotoxicity (Angelova et al. 2023) (Table 1).

On the other hand, compound 5c exhibited selective and predominant inhibitory activity against hMAO-B, reducing enzyme activity by 60% (Fig. 3). This selectivity for MAO-B is particularly relevant for enhancing dopaminergic transmission—an important therapeutic strategy for managing neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD). By preserving dopamine levels and reducing oxidative stress, 5c holds potential for alleviating motor symptoms and slowing neurodegeneration. However, this sulfonyl-hydrazone derivative, featuring a 5-methoxyindole scaffold, exhibited notably high cytotoxicity (Table 1).

The IC_{50} values were determined for the most active compounds (3e, 3f, 3i, 3r, 5a, and 5c) to evaluate their potency and selectivity toward hMAO-A and hMAO-B (Table 1). These values provided a quantitative measure of enzyme inhibition, enabling the calculation of the hMAO-B selectivity index (SI), defined as $IC_{50}(\text{hMAO-A})/IC_{50}(\text{hMAO-B})$. Compounds with SI values > 1 demonstrated a preference for hMAO-B, positioning them as promising candidates for further exploration in PD and AD therapies.

The selectivity index (SI) analysis revealed distinct inhibition profiles among the tested compounds. Compounds 3e and 3r exhibited dual MAO-A/B inhibition, effectively targeting both isoforms. This dual action suggests their potential as versatile modulators of monoaminergic pathways, which may offer therapeutic benefits in addressing the complex neurochemical imbalances observed in neurodegenerative disorders (Oyovwi et al. 2025). Dual inhibitors could offer broader symptom control—enhancing dopaminergic transmission via MAO-B inhibition while potentially regulating mood and neuroinflammation *via* MAO-A inhibition (Finberg and Rabey 2016).

Compound 3f demonstrated a notable preference for hMAO-B inhibition, as reflected by its high SI value. Since selective hMAO-B inhibitors are clinically valuable in

Parkinson's disease (PD)—slowing dopamine degradation, extending levodopa efficacy, and offering potential neuroprotection (Carradori et al. 2018)—3f emerges as a compelling candidate for further preclinical development.

In contrast, compound 3i exhibited marked hMAO-A selectivity, suggesting a different therapeutic direction. As hMAO-A is primarily involved in the metabolism of serotonin and norepinephrine, selective inhibition may offer antidepressant and anxiolytic effects, making 3i a potential lead for addressing the neuropsychiatric symptoms such as depression and anxiety that often co-occur with Alzheimer's disease (AD) and PD.

Compounds 5a and 5c stood out as potent and selective hMAO-B inhibitors, with IC_{50} values of $0.855 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{M}$ and $0.849 \pm 0.20 \mu\text{M}$, respectively, and high selectivity indices. While these values indicate moderate-to-strong inhibition, they remain less potent than standard MAO-B inhibitors like selegiline and rasagiline, which typically demonstrate nanomolar-range IC_{50} values. Nonetheless, these compounds were designed with multitarget potential, combining MAO-B inhibition with additional neuroprotective properties. This broader activity profile is advantageous in neurodegenerative conditions involving multiple pathological mechanisms. Their predominant hMAO-B inhibition, while sparing hMAO-A, suggests a favorable safety profile, minimizing serotonin-related side effects (e.g., hypertensive crises) that are commonly associated with non-selective MAO inhibitors. This selectivity makes them attractive candidates for PD therapy, supporting dopaminergic function without compromising serotonergic or noradrenergic systems.

In summary, compounds 3e, 3f, 3r, 5a, and 5c represent promising leads for further development. Their diverse selectivity profiles—from dual inhibition to MAO-B-specific targeting—offer a versatile platform for developing next-generation neuroprotective agents tailored to the multifactorial nature of PD and AD (Özdemir et al. 2021).

CYP3A4 inhibition assay

In the early discovery phase of this chemical series, the potential inhibitory effects on cytochrome P450 3A4

(CYP3A4), a key enzyme involved in the metabolism of a broad spectrum of clinically used drugs, were evaluated. This screening was performed to identify possible drug–drug interaction (DDI) liabilities, which are a major concern in the development of central nervous system (CNS)-active agents.

Within the 3a–3r compound series, several derivatives exhibited statistically significant inhibition of CYP3A4 activity. Specifically, compounds 3a, 3f, 3j, 3i, 3n, 3p, and 3q demonstrated approximately 30% inhibition of CYP3A4 enzymatic activity compared to the untreated control group (pure CYP3A4), with $P < 0.001$ (Fig. 5). This finding highlights the importance of further profiling these candidates for CYP450 isoform selectivity to mitigate potential metabolic liabilities in future preclinical studies.

This observed inhibition suggests a potential for pharmacokinetic interactions, which may affect the metabolic clearance of co-administered drugs. While moderate inhibition of CYP3A4 may enhance the bioavailability of certain therapeutics, it also carries the risk of increased toxicity or adverse effects due to impaired drug metabolism (Dresser et al. 2000). Therefore, careful consideration of the balance between therapeutic efficacy and metabolic

safety is crucial when advancing these compounds in drug development pipelines.

For the 5a–5l series, compounds 5a, 5h, 5i, and 5f exhibited a 35% reduction in CYP3A4 activity relative to the control (Fig. 6). Notably, the inhibitory effects observed across both series are comparable to ketoconazole, a standard CYP3A4 inhibitor, which reduced activity by 55%. This similarity suggests that these compounds may act through a similar inhibitory mechanism, contributing to a measurable reduction in enzyme activity.

While such inhibition could enhance the bioavailability of co-administered drugs metabolized by CYP3A4, it also raises significant concerns regarding potential drug–drug interactions (DDIs). These interactions may alter pharmacokinetics, leading to elevated plasma concentrations of CYP3A4 substrates, which could amplify therapeutic effects or increase the risk of dose-dependent toxicity. Therefore, further pharmacokinetic profiling and *in vivo* studies are necessary to evaluate the clinical relevance of these findings. Additionally, structural modifications should be explored to reduce CYP3A4 inhibition without compromising the compounds' target activity. These steps are crucial to minimizing DDI risks while preserving therapeutic efficacy.

Figure 5. Effect of 3a-r and ketoconazole in 1 μM concentration on CYP3A4 activity. *** $P < 0.001$ vs control (pure CYP3A4).

Figure 6. Effect of 5a-l and ketoconazole in 1 μM concentration on CYP3A4 activity. *** $P < 0.001$ vs control (pure CYP3A4).

Molecular docking study

In order to explain the activity of the synthesized compounds 3a–r and 5a–l, molecular docking studies were conducted at the binding sites of the MAO-B isoform. The thirty hydrazide-hydrazone and sulfonyl-hydrazone derivatives, as well as the native ligand SAG and selegiline, were subjected to molecular docking in the MAO-B crystallographic structure (PDB ID 2V5Z). Fig. 7 presents the 2D protein–ligand interaction (PLI) diagram of the co-crystallized ligand SAG in the ligand-binding domain of MAO-B. The presented diagram was obtained using the “Ligand Interactions” tool of MOE, with a maximum distance of 4.5 Å between heavy atoms of the ligand and receptor.

Figure 7. Interaction diagram of the co-crystallized ligand (S)-(+)-2-[4-(fluorobenzoyloxy-benzylamino)propionamide] (SAG) in the ligand-binding domain of MAO-B (PDB ID 2V5Z).

As seen from Fig. 7, Leu171 and Gln206 are involved in protein–ligand interactions, forming, respectively, arene-H and H-bonds. Residues Tyr60, Cys172, Ile199, Ile316, Tyr326, Phe343, Tyr398, and Tyr435 are at receptor exposure, very close to the ligand, but still not within binding distance.

During the molecular docking studies of the synthesized compounds 3a–r and 5a–l into the binding site of MAO-B, different docking protocols were explored, aiming at the investigation of the effect of docking parameters on the docking results. The following docking protocols (DP) were applied depending on the type of the post-placement refinement and the final scoring methodologies: DP1: rigid receptor/no final scoring; DP2: rigid receptor/London dG final scoring; DP3: rigid receptor/GBVI/WSA final scoring; DP4: induced fit/no final scoring; DP5: induced fit/London dG final scoring; DP6: induced fit/GBVI/WSA final scoring. The docking protocols have been validated by inspecting the binding energies and the RMSD values of the re-docked referent compound (selegiline). After a thorough comparative analysis, results obtained by DP1 are chosen to be presented as DP1 shows the most promising results towards the experimental investigations for the most active compounds (Table 2).

The docking scores of the compounds applying DP1 were found satisfactory in the range of -47.09 to -29.66, many of them lower than the docking score of the reference

Table 2. Docking scores of the investigated compounds in the active sites of MAO-B (PDB ID 2V5Z).

Compounds	S-score, kcal/mol	Compounds	S-score, kcal/mol
3a	-27.66	3q	-37.11
3b	-41.54	3r	-29.60
3c	-34.65	5a	-40.93
3d	-37.25	5b	-32.17
3e	-45.38	5c	-39.18
3f	-47.09	5d	-30.77
3g	-44.22	5e	-37.85
3h	-46.26	5f	-32.36
3i	-43.26	5g	-30.82
3j	-36.14	5h	-41.28
3k	-45.67	5i	-35.96
3l	-42.17	5j	-38.95
3m	-42.71	5k	-38.01
3n	-33.92	5l	-36.52
3o	-39.09	SAG	-39.92
3p	-38.87	Selegiline	-33.27

compound selegiline (-33.27). According to docking, the best compound is 3f with the lowest score of -47.09, followed by compounds 3h and 3k with docking scores of -46.26 and -45.67, respectively. Meanwhile, the compound 3f is the second one active. The most active compound, 3e, appears as the fourth best after docking. Table 2 summarizes the docking scores applying DP1 of all synthesized and referent compounds, while Table 3 presents a comparison between the most active compounds and their docking scores/ranks.

Table 3. Docking scores of the most active compounds in the active sites of MAO-B (PDB ID 2V5Z).

Compounds	S-score, kcal/mol	Ranking by docking score
3e	-45.38	4
3f	-47.09	1
3i	-43.26	6
3r	-29.60	31
5a	-40.93	11
Selegiline	-33.27	26

In addition to the analysis based on the docking scores (binding energies) of the most active compounds, a visual inspection of their best poses, along with those of selegiline, was also performed to ensure that the poses with the lowest docking scores correspond to the most reasonable binding modes of the compounds. PLI diagrams of the five most active compounds as well as of selegiline in the ligand-binding domain of MAO-B were presented in Fig. 8.

As seen from Fig. 8f, selegiline demonstrated two PLIs, namely one of the arene-H type with Ile199 and one H-bond with Gln206. Compounds 3i (Fig. 8c) and 5a (Fig. 8e) repeated one of the specific interactions of selegiline, those with Ile199 (particularly, of arene-H type in 3i and as H-bond in 5a). All five of the most active compounds (Fig. 8a–e) demonstrated newly recognized PLIs of the arene-arene type with Tyr435, while, in addition, the compound 3i (Fig. 8c) demonstrated an H-bond with Pro102, and the compound 3r (Fig. 8d) demonstrated PLIs of the arene-arene type with Tyr326 and Tyr398 and an H-bond with Cys172 (Table 4).

Figure 8. PLIs diagrams of (a) 3e, (b) 3f, (c) 3i, (d) 3r, (e) 5a, and (f) selegiline in the ligand-binding domain of MAO-B (PDB ID 2V5Z) (the legend is the same as that presented in Fig. 1).

Table 4. PLIs of the most active compounds in the active sites of MAO-B (PDB ID 2V5Z).

Compounds	Pro102	Cys172	Ile199	Gln206	Tyr326	Tyr398	Tyr435
Selegiline			✓	✓			
3e							✓
3f							✓
3i	✓		✓				✓
3r		✓			✓	✓	✓
5a			✓				✓

Presented results from molecular docking studies demonstrated the potential protein–ligand interactions of the investigated compounds, and, as such, they could be considered for further investigations.

Conclusion

This study characterized 30 hybrid derivatives, hydrazone (3a–r) and sulfonylhydrazone (5a–l) scaffolds, previously identified as multitarget-directed ligands (MTDLs) for neurodegenerative disorders, and evaluated their inhibitory activity against MAO-A, MAO-B, and CYP3A4. Compounds 3e, 3f, and 3r showed notable MAO-B inhibition, with 3f surpassing selegiline in potency and exhibiting strong hMAO-B selectivity. Compound 3i demonstrated stronger MAO-A inhi-

bitation than chorgyline, highlighting its potential as a multifunctional agent for Alzheimer’s disease, particularly in addressing both neurodegeneration and neuropsychiatric symptoms. Selectivity index analysis identified 3e, 3i, and 3r as dual MAO-A/B inhibitors, while 3f, 5a, and 5c showed clear MAO-B selectivity. Several compounds also exhibited moderate CYP3A4 inhibition, suggesting a potential risk for drug–drug interactions. The consistent inhibition profile across both series underscores the need to balance therapeutic efficacy with metabolic safety during lead optimization. Molecular docking studies supported the biological data, highlighting strong binding interactions, particularly for 3e and 3f, within the MAO-B active site, reinforcing their potential as lead candidates for Parkinson’s disease therapy. Overall, compounds 3f, 3i, 5a, and 5c stand out as promising lead structures for further development as selective MAO-B inhibitors and neuroprotective agents. Their structural versatility and target specificity highlight their suitability for tailored therapeutic strategies. These results lay a solid foundation for future structure–activity relationship (SAR) studies aimed at enhancing potency, selectivity, and safety. Further optimization of these multi-target-directed ligands (MTDLs) could lead to next-generation neuroprotective therapies for both Parkinson’s and Alzheimer’s diseases.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors, or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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